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New location of the well-known Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* (Wahlenberg, 1821) from north-western Poland

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ABSTRACT

This report documents the new location of the representative Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus*. This well-known trilobite was discovered in the “Storkowo” Mining Plant in the central part of the West Pomeranian Province in Poland.

Keywords: trilobite, *Asaphus expansus*, Wahlenberg, Ordovician, Paleozoic, north-western Poland

1. INTRODUCTION

The representative Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* is often found in Ordovician sedimentary rocks. This *Asaphus expansus* trilobite is found frequently in northern Poland. It is related to the deposited layers of postglacial material from Scandinavia, from the last glaciation [1-12].

The trilobites in these postglacial materials are often found as component parts of the entire trilobite. It is very rare to discover a whole specimen of one or another trilobite species, but quite often they are found as component parts of a trilobite, in the form of a pygidium.

2. SEARCH RESULT

The photos show the location of the Mining Plant in Storkowo, West Pomeranian Province, Poland (53.46 N, 15.60 E) (**Photos 1: A & B**).

Photo 1A. The Mining Plant in Storkowo, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

Photo 1B. The Mining Plant in Storkowo, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

The photos show the discovered trilobite (two specimens) from the area of the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland (**Photos 2: A & B**).

Photo 2A. Discovered Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* at the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland.

Photo 2B. Discovered Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* at the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland.

The photos show the discovered trilobite as component parts - a pygidium from the area of the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland (**Photos 3: A & B**).

Photo 3A. Discovered Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* in the form of a pygidium at the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland.

Photo 3B. Discovered Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* in the form of a pygidium at the Mining Plant in Storkowo, Poland.

3. CONCLUSION

The new discovery site of the Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* at the Mining Plant in Storkowo, West Pomeranian Province in Poland, is documented and entered into the world map of the species distribution.

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